

Bioremediation of mechanic workshop polluted soil amended with poultry litter

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the use of 40% w/w poultry litter to remedy soil polluted with spent oil released to the environment in mechanic workshops. Soil samples were obtained in pots, treated with poultry litter and observed for a period of 56 days. Pots A and B served as unpolluted and polluted control while pot C served as the polluted sample that was amended. The bacterial count ranged from 6.3×10^3 to 6.8×10^4 cfu/g in unpolluted soil (US), 8.0×10^3 to 9.8×10^4 cfu/g in mechanic workshop soil (MS) and 1.72×10^4 to 1.80×10^5 cfu/g mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter (MSAP). Fungi counts ranged from 2.5×10^3 to 3.0×10^4 cfu/g in US, 2.8×10^3 to 4.0×10^4 cfu/g in MS, and 9.2×10^3 to 1.68×10^5 cfu/g in MSAP. There were no significant differences in the bacteria and fungi counts at 5% probability level. Bacteria genera that were commonly isolated from the samples include *Bacillus sp.*, *Pseudomonas sp.*, *Micrococcus sp.*, *Staphylococcus sp.*, and *Proteus sp.* while fungi genera include *Aspergillus sp.*, *Mucor sp.* and *Saccharomyces sp.* There were no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in pH, moisture, nitrogen, organic carbon and electrical conductivity. However, significant differences were observed in organic matter and phosphorus between the treatments (US, MS, MSAP) at 5% probability level. The results of this work strongly support the use of poultry litter in reclaiming hydrocarbon polluted soil.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pollution especially with petroleum and petroleum products has been recognized as one of the most serious problems affecting lives of citizens and economies of nations [1]. Oil spills especially on large scale has rendered large areas of land unusable for agricultural activities. According to Opara [2], over 600 cases of oil spills were reported in the Niger delta areas of Nigeria in 2014.

One of the silent oil spills that go unnoticed in Nigeria is that of mechanic workshop where used oil and other petroleum products are released accidentally or deliberately to the environment. Ololade [3] reported that in Nigeria and most developing countries, there is an ever-increasing demand for personal vehicles, and this has led to increase in number of mechanic

workshops in the country and increase in their activities. Oil released to the environment causes serious harm not only to the soil fauna but also to plants, animals and humans. Disposing spent oil in the soil is a common practice in mechanic workshops [4]. Achuba and Clerke-peretiemo [5] reported that used engine oil, lubricating oil and petroleum products like petrol, diesel, are released to the soil when mechanics repair automobiles and generators or change motor oil. Osubor and Anoliefo [6] are of the opinion that oil is also released into the environment from the exhaust system during engine use and also from engine leaks. This spent oil contains substances that are toxic to the soil flora and fauna and also to man [4]. When rain falls, the oil on the surface may be washed to farm lands, into wells or underground, thus polluting ground water.

Bioremediation is the productive use of biodegradative process to remove or detoxify pollutants that are threat to public health [7]. It can be said to be nature's way of cleaning up itself. Alexander [8] opined that the goal of bioremediation is to transform organic pollutants into harmless metabolites or mineralize the pollutants into carbon dioxide and water. Before bioremediation can take place, the following must be present: (i) a contaminant; (ii) suitable microorganisms; and (iii) an electron acceptor [9].

Bioremediation methods are considered to be more economical and safe for treatment of oil polluted sites [10]. Some microorganisms have the ability to degrade large hydrocarbon and use them as food source [11]. These microorganisms can degrade a vast number of hydrocarbon compounds and can be used in cleaning up contaminated sites [12]. Jobson *et al.* [13] pointed out that bacteria and fungi are the only biological species which have the metabolic capability of utilizing hydrocarbon for cell synthesis. Among the bacterial groups capable of using hydrocarbons include species of *Pseudomonas*, *Marinobacter*, *Alcanivorax*, *Sphingomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Cellulomonas*, *Dietzia*, *Gordonia*, *Acinetobacter*, *Mycobacterium*, *Alcaligenes*, *Corynebacterium*, *Flavobacterium*, *Arthrobacter*, *Cytophaga*, *Xanthomonas* and *Bacillus* [14]. Of the fungi groups, molds like *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Amorphoteca*, *Neosartorya*, *Paecilomyces*, *Talaromyces*, *Graphium* and yeasts like *Candida*, *Yarrowia* and *Pichia* have been implicated [15]. However, bacteria are the most active agents in petroleum degradation, working as primary degraders of spilled oil in the environment [16]. According to Fritsche and Hofrichter [14], a single microorganism does not possess the enzymatic capability to degrade all or even most of the organic compounds in a polluted soil. They believe mixed microbial communities have the most powerful biodegradative potential because the genetic information of more than one organism is necessary to degrade the complex mixtures of organic compounds present in contaminated areas.

Hochmuth *et al.* [17] observed that poultry litter which is a mixture of poultry manure, bedding materials like wood shaving or sawdust and feathers, is rich in nutrients such as nitrate, phosphorus, potassium as well as organisms capable of utilizing hydrocarbons [18]. The most common source of poultry litter is the broiler houses or poultry farms [17]. Obasi *et al.* [19] reported that poultry manure is richer in nutrients compared to cow manure, sawdust and horse manure. In addition, poultry litter helps to increase the moisture holding capacity of soil, lowers its bulk density and improve overall structure [20]. Poultry litter has been used to remedy polluted environments by many researchers. Adams *et al.* [21] used poultry litter to amend soil polluted with spent oil. Okwute and Ijah used it to amend soil polluted with palm

oil mill effluent [22] ; [23]. Nwadinigwe and Onyeidu [24] also used poultry manure (as biostimulant) along with a mixed culture of *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* to remedy crude oil polluted soil.

Mechanic workshop soil is relatively poor for agricultural purposes [25]. Many abandoned mechanic workshops are lying fallow with black hardened soil surfaces [4]. Hence there is the need to reclaim the abandoned workshop soils for agricultural purposes using cheap and readily available organic manure. Poultry litter is a biodegradable waste and it is non-toxic to the soil microflora. It is cheaper to use than inorganic fertilizers such as N:P:K (15: 15: 15). The significance of this study lies in the use of this cheap and readily available poultry litter to speed up the bioremediation of mechanic workshop polluted soil.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample Collection

Soil samples were collected from a mechanic workshop opposite Kogi State University (KSU) First gate, Ankpa road, Anyigba. The samples were collected at a depth of 0-5cm from three different points into two perforated plastic pots labelled A and B, while another soil sample was collected from soil of the Faculty of Natural Sciences into the third pot (C) which served as the control for this study.

All the pots contained 6.0kg of soil each. Pot A contained only mechanic workshop soil. In pot B, 2.4kg of poultry litter (40% amendment level) was incorporated into the soil while C contained unpolluted soil (control). The three soil samples were kept in the Biological garden, Kogi State University, Anyigba and were watered twice a week for a period of eight weeks.

2.2 Sampling

Sampling started two weeks after amendment. Subsequent soil samples were collected every two weeks for duration of eight (8) weeks to determine the microbiological components and physicochemical properties of the soil.

2.3 Microbiological and physicochemical analysis

The soil samples from the three pots were analyzed microbiologically to estimate the total bacterial and fungal counts. Serial dilutions of the soil [26] were carried out and inoculation was made aseptically from 10^4 dilutions onto Nutrient Agar (NA) plates for bacteria and Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) plates for fungi. The NA plates were incubated at 37°C while the SDA plates were incubated at room temperature.

pH of the soil was determined at ambient temperature using glass electrode pH and conductivity meter (Hannia, Italy) in 1:1 water to

soil ratio. Nitrogen was determined by the micro Kjeldahl method as described by Persson *et al.* [27]. Phosphorus was determined by the Murphy and Riley [28] method. The ignition method of Akinsanmi [29] was used to determine the organic matter content while the dry weight method of Tropical Development Institute, TDI [30] was used to determine the moisture content. Descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using procedure of SPSS version 16 (2007). Experimental precision achieved was reported at $p \leq 0.05$ level.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Bacterial counts

Figure 1 shows the total viable counts of bacteria obtained from unpolluted soil, mechanic workshop soil and mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter. The bacterial counts

ranged from 6.3×10^3 to 6.8×10^4 cfu/g in unpolluted soil (US), 8.0×10^3 to 9.8×10^4 cfu/g in mechanic workshop soil (MS), and 1.72×10^4 to 1.8×10^5 cfu/g in mechanic workshop soil amended poultry litter (MSAP). The bacterial counts were higher in MSAP compared to MS and US. There were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in the bacterial counts between US, MS and MSAP.

3.2 Bacterial Isolates and frequency of occurrence

Table 1 shows the frequency of occurrence of bacteria isolated from the samples. *Bacillus* sp had the highest frequency of occurrence (32.14%) followed by *Micrococcus* sp (25%), *Proteus* sp (14.29%) while *Escherichia coli* had the lowest frequency of occurrence (7.14%). Other bacteria isolated were *Pseudomonas* sp (10.71%) and *Staphylococcus* sp (10.71%).

Fig 1. Total viable bacterial counts obtained from mechanic workshop soil.

US: Unpolluted soil; MS: Mechanic workshop soil; MSAP: Mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter

Table 1. Frequency and occurrence of bacteria isolated from mechanic workshop soil.

Isolates	US	MS	MSAP	Total	Percentage (%)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	4	3	2	9	32.14
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	–	1	1	2	7.14
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	2	1	4	7	25.00
<i>Proteus</i> sp	–	3	1	4	14.29
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	1	2	–	3	10.71
<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	1	–	2	3	10.71
Total	8	10	10	28	100

US: Unpolluted soil; MS: Mechanic workshop soil; MSAP: Mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter

3.3 Fungal Counts

Figure 2 shows the total viable counts of fungi obtained from US, MS and MSAP during the study. The fungal counts ranged from 2.5×10^3 to 3.0×10^4 cfu/g in US, 2.8×10^3 to 4.0×10^4 cfu/g in MS and 9.2×10^3 cfu/g to 1.68×10^4 cfu/g in MSAP. MSAP had the highest fungal counts throughout the study and a slight increase in fungal count was observed in MS on day 42. There were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in the fungal counts between US, MS and MSAP.

3.4 Fungal Isolates and frequency of occurrence

Table 2 shows the frequency of occurrence of the fungal isolates. *Mucor* sp. had the highest frequency of occurrence (45%) followed by *Saccharomyces* sp. (20.83%) while *A. flavus* had the least frequency of occurrence (4.7%). Other fungi isolated were *Aspergillus fumigatus* (8.30%), *A. niger* (12.50%) and *Microsporium* sp. (8.30%).

3.5 Physicochemical characteristics of mechanic workshop soil

Table 3 shows the physicochemical characteristics of mechanic workshop soil undergoing bioremediation. The mean pH ranged from 6.22 ± 0.23 to 7.47 ± 0.47 . MS had the least pH while an almost nutrient pH was observed in MSAP. There were no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the pH at 5% probability level between US, MS and MSAP.

The highest moisture content was observed in MSAP ($11.40 \pm 3.17\%$) followed by MS ($8.11 \pm 1.66\%$) and US ($7.01 \pm 3.68\%$). There were no

significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in the moisture content between the treatments.

The nitrogen content was low in both US ($0.90 \pm 0.22\%$) and MS ($0.19 \pm 0.32\%$) compared to MSAP ($9.61 \pm 9.24\%$). There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the nitrogen content at 5% probability level in US, MS and MSAP.

Linear increase in phosphorus concentration was observed in the soil samples. Phosphorus concentration in US was less than that of MS and MS was also lower than that of MSAP. The phosphorus concentration ranged from $8.06 \pm 0.94\%$ to $14.06 \pm 2.88\%$. Significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) were observed in the phosphorus concentrations in US, MS and MSAP.

The organic carbon in both US and MS were low compared to MSAP. The organic carbon ranged from 0.60 ± 0.44 - $6.34 \pm 4.44\%$. The highest organic carbon was observed in MSAP while the lowest value was observed in US. There were no significant differences in the organic carbon in US, MS and MSAP at 5% probability level.

Similar trend in the organic carbon was observed in the organic matter content. the highest organic matter content was observed in the amended mechanic workshop polluted soil (MSAP) followed by MS ($1.80 \pm 0.10\%$) and oil free soil, US (1.04 ± 0.07). However, there were significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) in the organic matter content in US, MS and MSAP.

The electrical conductivity was low in the soil samples regardless of treatment. It ranged from 0.50 ± 0.11 uS to 1.23 ± 0.95 uS. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the electrical conductivity of the soil samples.

Fig. 2. Total fungi count obtained from mechanic workshop soil undergoing bioremediation. US: unpolluted soil; MS: mechanic workshop soil, MSAP: mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter.

Table 2. Frequency of occurrence of Fungi isolated from mechanic workshop soil.

Isolates	US	MS	MSAP	Total	Percentage %)
<i>A. flavus</i>	1	–	–	1	4.17
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	–	2	–	2	8.30
<i>A. niger</i>	1	1	1	3	12.5
<i>Microsporum</i> sp.	–	–	2	2	8.30
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	5	5	1	11	45.83
<i>Saccharomyces</i> sp	–	1	4	5	20.83
Total	7	9	8	24	100

US: unpolluted soil; MS : mechanic workshop soil; MSAP: mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter

Table 3. Physicochemical qualities of mechanic workshop polluted soil (M+SE).

Parameter	US	MS	MSAP
pH	6.40 ± 0.30 ^a	6.22 ± 0.23 ^a	7.24 ± 0.47 ^a
Moisture (%)	7.01 ± 3.68 ^a	8.11 ± 1.66 ^a	11.40 ± 3.17 ^a
Nitrogen (%)	0.90 ± 0.22 ^a	0.19 ± 0.32 ^a	9.61 ± 9.24 ^a
Phosphorus (%)	8.06 ± 0.94 ^b	10.40 ± 1.00 ^{a, b}	14.06 ± 2.88 ^a
Organic carbon (%)	0.60 ± 0.44 ^a	1.04 ± 0.06 ^a	6.34 ± 4.44 ^a
Organic matter (%)	1.04 ± 0.07 ^c	1.80 ± 0.10 ^b	3.20 ± 0.30 ^a
Electrical conductivity (US)	0.50 ± 0.11 ^a	0.49 ± 0.16 ^a	1.23 ± 0.95 ^a

a,b,c: means denoted by different superscripts along the same row are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

US: Unpolluted soil, MS: Mechanic workshop soil, MSAP: Mechanic workshop soil amended with poultry litter.

4. DISCUSSION

The microbiological results showed that the bacterial counts were higher in mechanic workshop soils than the unpolluted soil. This might be due to the presence of indigenous microorganisms capable of utilizing petroleum hydrocarbon as food substrates, thus proliferating in the soil. Thapa *et al.* [7] reported that some microorganisms are able to degrade hydrocarbon and use them as sole source of carbon and energy for growth. It could also be because the organisms had adapted to the polluted environment. This would mean that the process of intrinsic bioremediation was on course already. Hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria like *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Micrococcus*, *Staphylococcus* and *Proteus* were frequently isolated from the soil samples. Stephen *et al.* [31] observed higher bacterial counts in oil (diesel) free soil than diesel polluted soil, contrary to the result of this study. They attributed the low count in the polluted soil to the inability of some microorganisms to withstand the high level of diesel concentration (11.11% pollution level).

The oil polluted soil amended with poultry litter had the highest bacterial counts throughout the study. This is in line with the findings of Willis *et al.* [32] and Okwute and Ijah [23]. They reported that chemical, microbiological and

physicochemical characteristics of poultry litter makes it a suitable co-substrate and nutrient source for microorganisms to thrive when applied to a polluted soil. The bacterial counts gradually decreased throughout the study and this might be as a result of exhaustion of the food substrate in the soil. Similar observation in the fall in microbial counts with time was reported by Aboaba *et al.* [25] in their study on bioremediation of agricultural soils polluted with crude oil.

The total viable fungal counts followed a similar pattern as bacterial counts except for a slight increase in MS on day 42. This increase might be due to fall in pH in MS on day 42. Rousk *et al.* [33] observed exponential increase in fungal counts with decreasing pH from 8.0 to 4.5. This proves that acidic pH favors fungal growth. Hydrocarbonoclastic fungi like *Aspergillus*, *Mucor*, *Microsporum* and *Saccharomyces* were frequently isolated during the study. This is similar to the findings of Adams *et al.* [21]. These authors isolated *Aspergillus*, *Mucor* and *Saccharomyces* from spent oil contaminated soil.

The result of the pH in this study tends towards neutrality. These results agree with the report of Amadi *et al.* [34] who observed that oil pollution increases soil acidity, and Zhang [35], who reported that application of organic manure

significantly increases soil pH towards neutrality. Also, studies have shown that most organisms capable of metabolizing hydrocarbons develop best at pH conditions close to neutrality [36]. Thus higher pH range (6 to 9) provides better conditions for mineralization of hydrocarbons. With the gradual exhaustion of the organic substrates, the pH of MS and MSAP appeared to tend towards neutrality.

The moisture content was higher in MSAP compared to US and MS. This may be due to the addition of poultry litter. Atlas and Bartha [37] reported that application of organic manure to soil improves the soil water holding capacity, bulk density and nutrients' mobilization for plants.

Nitrogen and phosphorus was observed to have gradually risen in MS and MSAP and fluctuated in US during the 56-day period. This may be due to nitrogen compounds in oil as well as the poultry litter used for amending MSAP. Ijah and Abioye [38] and Stephen *et al.* [39] reported increases in these two parameters in soil polluted by petroleum hydrocarbon and suggested that this could be due to higher organic matter contents of the oil polluted soil. Moreover, the addition of poultry litter might have increased both the phosphorus and nitrogen content of MSAP.

The increased level of organic carbon in MSAP may be due to the addition of poultry litter to the polluted soil, confirming the reports of Tanee and Kinako [35] that organic manure has the capability to increase soil nutrient by supplementing limiting nutrients.

Organic matter content was also higher in MS and MSAP than US. Increase in percentage organic matter observed in MS in this study had been observed earlier by Amadi *et al.* [33], Ogboghodo *et al.* [40] and Onuh *et al.* [41]. They all attributed it to the microbial mineralization of the oil in the mechanic workshop soil. However, in this study, the poultry litter might have contributed to the quick mineralization of the oil and the increase in the organic matter content observed.

Higher Electrical conductivity in MSAP than in US and MS are indicative that the treated soil has more soluble nutrients or salt that would improve the activity of the microorganisms (39). However, excessive salts in soils can result in poor structure, affect the water balance and limit the growth of soil organisms (39).the result therefore implies that MSAP higher amount of soluble nutrients available for absorption by plants and microorganisms. These nutrients exist as cations and anions; that dissolve in water for easy uptake by organisms [39].

5. CONCLUSION

The addition of poultry litter to the polluted soil led to the overall improvement in the soil physicochemical characteristics. Microbial population and activities also increased upon

treatment. More microorganisms were isolated from the treated soil than the untreated soil samples throughout the study. The results of this work strongly support the use of poultry litter in reclaiming hydrocarbon polluted soil.

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